

ISic1491

I.Sicily inscription 1491

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Enna

Place of origin (modern)

Enna

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329723

1. ἀρχὸς
2. Δαμ (ατριαστᾶν)
3. Ἐνναίων.
- 4.
5. [ὁ δεῖνα] ἀρχὸς
6. [τοῦ κοινοῦ τῶν] Δαμ-
7. [ατριαστᾶν] Ἐνναίων.
- 8.

Edition: PHI336905

1. Ἄρχος
2. Δάμ α [τρι]
3. Ἐνναίων.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644997

PHI 329723

PHI 336905

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 388-391
fig.15-16

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1491. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385964>